

CAPITAL STRUCTURE AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF LISTED MANUFACTURING COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The study focused on the impact of capital structure on the financial performance of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study specifically aim to determine the relationship between equity capital, debt capital and return on asset as a proxy of financial performance. The study adopts an ex-post facto research design. Data for the study was obtained from audited annual reports and accounts of the 10 sampled manufacturing firms listed in the Nigerian Exchange Group for a period of 10 years covering 2013 to 2023. Both descriptive and inferential statistics was employed to analyze the data while regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses. The result reveals that equity capital has a positive and significant impact on return on asset. Debt has a negative and significant impact on return on asset. The study recommends among others that manufacturing companies should strive for a balanced capital structure that maximizes the benefits of equity while minimizing effects of excessive debt. Manufacturing companies should regularly monitor their debt levels not to exceed manageable thresholds.*

Keywords: *Capital structure, Return on asset, Equity, Debt, Financial Performance.*

INTRODUCTION

Businesses, large or small require funds to perform their operations and attract investment opportunities. According to Singh and Bagga (2019), liberaalisation of economic policies globally has expanded investment opportunities, increased financing options and dependence on capital markets. Financing decision is a primary decision that must be made by businesses due to the associated risk. These decisions are crucial as it helps firms determine the best mix of capital and sources of finance in order to minimize total cost of capital and maximize their financial performance (Sike, Ibrahim & Maitala, 2023).

Capital structure is a mix of equity and debt which is a critical determinant of its financial health and performance. It gives firm a competitive advantage and adjust to dynamism of the business

environment both internal and external environment (Sike et al, 2023). The capital structure of any company remains bedrock for its existence either for commencement of a new operations or expansion of existing operation (Etale, 2020). Company's risk profile, cost of capital, market value and profitability are significantly influence by the composition of firm's capital structure. Capital structure decisions are centered on choosing between equity and debt. Research indicates that the optimal mix of equity and debt influences key financial indicators such as return on assets, return on equity, and net profit margin, impacting overall profitability and market value (Clement & Adesina, 2022).

The Nigeria's manufacturing sector is a cornerstone of the country's industrial base and a valuable contributor to Gross Domestic Product. As of recent years, the sector has accounted for approximately 10% of the national GDP, providing employment to millions and playing a pivotal role in economic diversification efforts away from oil dependency. Listed manufacturing companies on the Nigerian Exchange Group are pivotal players in this sector, driving innovation, productivity, and economic growth. However, despite the its role in the development and growth of the countries, Nigerian manufacturing companies face unique challenges such as fluctuating interest rates, volatile exchange rates, and regulatory changes affecting their capital structure decisions and financial performance.

Given the challenges faced by the manufacturing sector in Nigeria, including high production costs and economic fluctuations, strategic capital structure management is essential for sustaining growth, improving profitability, and driving economic diversification efforts. These challenges necessitate a careful consideration of capital structure to optimize financial performance in the manufacturing sector. Considering this problem, several studies have been conducted in this to look at impact of capital structure on financial performance. While some studies have found that long-term debt ratios have a negative relationship with return on assets, other shows that short-term debt, total debt ratios, and total equity ratios have positive significant influences on financial performance, emphasizing the importance of capital structure decisions in enhancing firm value and operational efficiency (Akinrinola, Tomori & Audu, 2023)

While there is extensive literature on the relationship between capital structure and financial performance in developed economies, the evidence in developing economies like Nigeria is less conclusive. This study aims to fill this gap by investigating how capital structure influences financial performance among listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- Determine the relationship between equity capital and return on assets of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.
- Examine the effect of debt capital on the return on assets of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

The hypothesis of the study stated in null form are;

Ho1: Equity Capita does not have significant relationship with the return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Ho2: Debt Capital does not have significant relationship with the return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Capital Structure

Capital structure has been defined differently by authors. A significant number of scientific works by authors from different countries of the world are devoted to the issue of consideration of the capital structure, problems of its optimization and search for effective ways of management from the position of maximizing the value of the corporation (Hrynyuk, Dokillenko, Levchenko & Trynychuk, 2023). Capital structure, according to Olaoye, Akintola, Soetan and Olusola (2020), involves the taking a decision on the best way to combine various sources of funds a firm uses to finance its operations and capital investments. Capital structure is therefore the combination of debt and equity used by firms to run their long term and short-term operations. It encompasses various long-term funding sources such as equity share capital, reserves, loans, and debentures, impacting a firm's value and the Weighted Average Cost of Capital (Hrynyuk et al, 2023).

Bond issue or long-term notes payable come as debt, while common stock, preferred stock or retained earnings are classified as equity. Another part of capital structure is working capital as short-term debt. Capital structure can be a composite of firm's short-term debt, longterm debt, common and preferred equity. When analyzing capital structure, the proportion of short and long-term debt needs to be considered. Analysts are most likely referring capital structure to a firm's debt-to-equity (D/E) ratio which provides the foresight of how risky a company is. A company that is heavily financed by debt usually has more aggressive capital structure and therefore poses greater risk to investors.

Capital structure is essentially concerned with how a firm finances its overall operations and progress by using different sources of funds" (Martinez, Scherger & Guercio, 2019). According to Stoiljkovic, Tomi and Uelac (2021), deciding on capital structure is one of the most important issues, given that capital structure largely determines the future performance of the company,. Trif, Dutu & Tuleu (2019) opine that organization performance is the primary goal of any type of firm, being a top priority for managers.

According to Wardini, Anugrah, Farid and Laili (2022), optimal capital structure plays a crucial role in influencing dividend policy. High dividend payouts are perceived positively by investors, signaling the company's good health and leading to increased share prices (Akib, Nurdin Purnaman & Anwar, 2023). Managing capital structure to maximize Return on Equity (ROE) involves balancing financial risk and profitability, with tools like financial leverage optimization and sensitivity analysis contributing to effective decision-making (Ferrabi, Schuhman & Zhu, 2022). By considering factors such as debt-to-equity ratios, profitability, and dividend policies, companies can enhance their financial performance and maintain investor confidence, ultimately impacting stock prices and overall market

dynamics (Hrynyuk et al, 2023). Modigliani and Miller's pioneering work in the 1950s proposed that the capital structure of a firm does not affect its market value under certain assumptions, such as no taxes, no transaction costs, and perfect markets.

Equity Capital

Equity capital, also known as shareholders' equity or owner's equity, represents the residual interest in the assets of a company after deducting its liabilities (Kumari, 2021). In other words, it is the amount of money that would be returned to a company's shareholders if all of the company's assets were liquidated and all of its debts were paid off. It refers to the ownership interest in a company represented by shares of stock. It comprises the funds contributed by shareholders (both common and preferred) and the retained earnings accumulated over time (Barr & Picton, 2022). Equity capital plays a vital role in a company's capital structure, offering stability and confidence to creditors and investors by representing the residual interest after deducting liabilities. (Polsky, 2022).

Equity capital can come from two main sources: common stock and retained earnings. Common stock refers to the shares of a company that are owned by its shareholders (Singh, Aggarwai & Mathur, 2023). When a company issues new shares of common stock, it receives cash in exchange for those shares, which increases its equity capital. Retained earnings, on the other hand, represent the portion of a company's profits that have been reinvested back into the business rather than being distributed to shareholders as dividends (Suleiman, Popoola & Yahaya, 2022). Over time, as a company generates profits and retains some of them, its retained earnings will grow, increasing its equity capital (Singh et al 2023).

According to Naoaj and Hosen (2023), It is important for companies to maintain adequate levels of equity capital because it provides a cushion against losses and helps ensure their financial stability. A strong equity base allows a company to borrow money more easily and at lower interest rates, since lenders view companies with higher levels of equity as less risky. Additionally, equity capital gives a company greater flexibility to make investments and pursue growth opportunities.

However, it is also possible for a company to have too much equity capital. If a company has an excessively high level of equity relative to its debt, it may not be taking full advantage of leverage, which can limit its ability to generate returns for shareholders. Therefore, managing equity capital requires striking a balance between maintaining financial stability and maximizing profitability (Yen, Huong & Anh, 2023).

Debt Capital

Debt capital refers to the funds that a company raises through borrowing, such as loans or bonds. Unlike equity capital, which represents ownership in the company, debt capital involves repaying the principal amount borrowed plus interest over a specified period of time (Dewi & Damsar, 2023). The sources of debt capital include banks, credit unions, bond investors, and other lending institutions.

Debt capital can provide several benefits for companies. It offers a way to raise large amounts of capital quickly without diluting ownership interests (Rogoff, 2020). It also typically comes with lower interest rates compared to equity financing, making it a cost-effective option for funding operations, investing in new projects, or refinancing existing debt. Furthermore, interest payments on debt capital are tax-deductible, reducing a company's overall tax liability (Rogoff, 2020).

However, there are also risks associated with debt capital. Borrowing too much can lead to high fixed costs, putting pressure on a company's cash flow and potentially leading to default (McConnell & Perez-Quiros, 2015). Moreover, debt holders have priority over equity holders in terms of claims on a company's assets in case of bankruptcy or liquidation. As a result, excessive debt levels can increase a company's vulnerability to economic downturns or industry disruptions.

Therefore, managing debt capital requires careful consideration of a company's financial situation, including its cash flows, revenue streams, and risk profile. Companies should aim to strike a balance between leveraging debt capital to fund growth while minimizing financial risk. This often involves regularly reviewing debt agreements, monitoring interest rate trends, and assessing potential refinancing options to optimize debt structures and reduce costs (Greenwood & Hanson, 2013). Effective management of debt capital is critical for ensuring long-term financial sustainability and creating value for stakeholders (Calomiris & Haber, 2014).

Financial Performance

Financial performance refers to a company's ability to generate revenues, control costs, and create value for its shareholders (Ramirez & Rodriguez). The financial performance of a company is a measure of its financial health and its ability to generate profits from its operations and assets. In this study, financial performance is assessed using the Return on Assets (ROA) metric, which indicates how effectively a company utilizes its assets to generate earnings. The impact of capital structure, specifically equity and debt, on financial performance is crucial for understanding how different financing decisions influence a firm's profitability (Team, Crowe & Vaidya, 2024).

Return on Assets (ROA) is a financial metric that measures a company's efficiency in utilizing its assets to generate income (Hasnan, et al, 2015). Specifically, ROA is calculated by dividing a company's net income by its total assets. Higher ROA values indicate that a company is generating more income per naira of assets, suggesting efficient use of resources and strong profitability. Conversely, lower ROA values suggest that a company is struggling to generate sufficient income relative to its assets, indicating potential operational or strategic challenges (Fuller, 2020).

Analysts and investors often compare ROA across different industries and companies to gauge relative performance. While specific benchmarks vary depending on factors such as industry norms and macroeconomic conditions, generally speaking, ROAs above 5% are considered solid, while ROAs below 2% may raise concerns about a company's profitability (Gerstenbery & Patel, 2016). In addition to

providing insights into a company's overall profitability, ROA can help identify areas where operational efficiencies could be improved (Hartmann, Moeller & Schmid, 2017).

Theoretical Review

The study is anchored on the trade-off theory of capital structure. The theory is based on the assumption that firms should optimise the mix of equity and debt in their capital structure to reduce their weighted average cost of capital. In other words, it suggests that companies should balance the tax advantages of debt financing against the costs of financial distress. According to this theory, there is an optimal capital structure where the marginal benefit of the tax shield equals the marginal cost of financial distress.

The trade-off theory of capital structure is the idea that a company chooses how much debt finance and how much equity finance to use by balancing the costs and benefits. An important purpose of the theory is to explain the fact that corporations usually are financed partly with debt and partly with equity. It states that there is an advantage to financing with debt, the tax benefits of debt and there is a cost of financing with debt, the costs of financial distress including bankruptcy costs of debt and non-bankruptcy costs.

However, the theory has been criticized on different ground. The theory overemphasis on tax benefits of debt. It places a strong emphasis on debt which may not be as significant as significant for high-tax burden profitable firms. It fails to fully consider non-financial factors that influence a company's capital structure decisions such as management preferences, agency conflicts and industry norms. It is challenging to accurately determine the costs of financial bankruptcy and distress.

Despite these challenges, it provides a useful framework for and analyzing and understanding a firm's capital structure decisions. For the purpose of this, the trade-off theory of capital structure provides a valuable framework for understanding the findings of this study on the impact of capital structure on the financial performance, particularly the return on assets (ROA), of manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group.

Based on the above empirical studies, most studies such as those by Ajibola, Wisdom, and Qudus (2018), and Olayemi and Fakayode (2021) analyze the impact of capital structure on financial performance across different sectors or have a broad focus on listed firms. Although some focus specifically on manufacturing firms, there is a limited exploration of how capital structure impacts financial performance within this specific sector in the Nigerian context. Various methodologies are employed in existing studies, including panel ordinary least squares (OLS), regression analysis, and descriptive statistics. While these methods provide valuable insights, there is often a lack of consistency in findings due to differences in the models used and variables examined. To fill these gaps, the current study focus on examining the impact of capital structure on financial performance particularly in manufacturing companies listed in the Nigerian Exchange Group by using Hausman test to determine the most appropriate method of analysis to be adopted.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopts ex-post facto research design. The population includes all listed manufacturing companies on the Nigerian Exchange Group formerly Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). A sample of 10 companies is selected based on the availability and completeness of financial data for a period of 10years (2014-2023). The time series data was obtained from the annual accounts and reports of the selected companies, leading to a total of 100 observations.

For the purpose of the data analysis, Descriptive Statistics was used to summarised all variables, including means, standard deviations, and ranges. Correlation Analysis was adopted to identify the strength and direction of relationships between variables, while Random Effects model employed based on the results of the Hausman test to assess the impact of capital structure proxies on financial performance proxy. All the analyses were performed using Eviews statistical software, version 8.1. The multiple regression model is presented as follows:

$$ROA = f(EQT, DBT)$$

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1EQT_{it} + \beta_2DBT_{it} + e_{it}$$

Where,

ROA= Return on assets

EQT = Equity capital

DBT = Debt capital

β_0 = Constant term

$\beta_1 - \beta_1$ = coefficients of the independent variables

e_{it} = Stochastic error

ANALYSIS AND RESULT

The section provides the results from the descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation and multiple regression – random effect model.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

	ROA	EQTY	DEBT
Mean	0.048456	47704924	1.07E+08
Median	0.043252	29794104	45657951
Maximum	0.264935	1.82E+08	6.60E+08
Minimum	-0.300952	-78035156	-8480683.
Std. Dev.	0.088915	48700824	1.42E+08
Skewness	-0.398941	0.975135	1.883802
Kurtosis	4.693688	3.556920	6.343066
Jarque-Bera	14.60498	17.14045	105.7122
Probability	0.000674	0.000190	0.000000
Sum	4.845614	4.77E+09	1.07E+10

Sum Sq. Dev.	0.782679	2.35E+17	2.00E+18
Observations	100	100	100

Source: Researcher’s computation using E-views 8

The average return on assets of approximately 4.85%, indicates the overall profitability of the firms relative to their total assets. The median value of 4.33% is close to the mean, suggesting a somewhat symmetric distribution around the mean. The highest ROA recorded is 26.49%, showing that some firms achieved significant profitability. The lowest ROA is -30.09%, indicating some firms experienced significant losses. 8.89%, reflecting moderate variability in the profitability of the firms. The Skewness value of 0.398941 indicates a slight left skew, meaning more values are concentrated on the right side of the mean with fewer extreme negative values. The Kurtosis (4.693688), which is higher than 3, indicates a leptokurtic distribution with heavier tails than a normal distribution. The Jarque-Bera statistic of 14.60498 and a probability of 0.000674, implies that the data deviates significantly from normality.

The average equity of 47.70 million Naira shows the average capital held by the firms. The median equity of approximately 29.79 million Naira indicates that half of the firms have equity less than this amount, showing a central tendency lower than the mean. The highest recorded equity of 182 million Naira indicates significant capital in some firms. The minimum equity of -78.04 million Naira reflects firms with negative equity, possibly indicating financial distress. Standard Deviation of 48.70 million Naira shows a significant variability in the equity levels among the firms. The Skewness of 0.975135, indicates a positive skew, meaning more firms have equity below the mean, with fewer extreme high values. The Kurtosis value (3.556920), slightly above 3, suggests a distribution with moderately heavy tails. The Jarque-Bera statistic of 17.14045 and a probability of 0.000190 indicate significant deviation from normality.

The average debt of 107 million Naira indicates the average amount of debt carried by the firms. The median debt of approximately 45.66 million Naira shows that half of the firms have debt less than this amount. The highest recorded debt of 660 million Naira, indicates some firms have substantial debt. The minimum debt is -8.48 million Naira. The Standard Deviation of 142 million Naira, indicates a substantial variability in debt levels among firms. The Skewness of 1.883802, indicates a strong positive skew, with most firms having debt below the mean and fewer firms with very high debt levels. The Kurtosis of 6.343066, much higher than 3, indicates a leptokurtic distribution with very heavy tails. The Jarque-Bera with a statistic of 105.7122 and a probability of 0.000000, indicates that the data shows a very significant deviation from normality.

Correlation Analysis

Table 2 Correlation Result

	ROA	EQTY	DEBT
ROA	1.000000	0.062329	-0.258820

EQTY	1.000000	0.451566
DEBT		1.000000

Source: Researcher’s computation using E-views 8

The correlation coefficient between ROA and EQTY is 0.062329, indicating a weak positive relationship. This suggests that changes in a firm's equity are weakly associated with changes in its return on assets. This weak correlation implies that equity does not strongly influence the firm's profitability as measured by ROA.

The correlation between ROA and DEBT is -0.258820, indicating a weak to moderate negative relationship. This suggests that as debt increases, ROA tends to decrease. In other words, higher levels of debt are generally associated with lower profitability, which aligns with the conventional understanding that excessive debt can be detrimental to a firm's financial performance.

Normality Test Analysis

The normality of the standardized residuals was assessed using graphical methods and the Jarque-Bera test. The histogram of the residuals shows a roughly symmetric distribution around zero, but with heavy tails, as indicated by a kurtosis value of 5.162876. The skewness value of -0.262318 suggests a slight left skew. The Jarque-Bera test statistic was 20.63865 with a p-value of 0.000033, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis of normality at the 0.05 significance level. These results suggest that the residuals do not follow a normal distribution, primarily due to high kurtosis.

Hausman Test

The Hausman test was conducted to determine the appropriateness of the random effects model (REM) versus the fixed effects model (FEM) for analyzing the impact of equity (EQTY) and debt (DEBT) on return on assets (ROA). The test statistics are summarized below:

Statistic	Value
Chi-Sq. Statistic	3.520887
Chi-Sq. d.f.	2
Prob.	0.1720

The test results show a p-value of 0.1720, leading us to fail to reject the null hypothesis that the random effects model is appropriate. This implies 0.000000 that there is no significant evidence that the random effects are correlated with the regressors, validating the use of the random effects model for this study.

Multiple Regression Analysis

The random effects model was employed to examine the impact of equity and debt on return on assets (ROA) while assuming random firm-specific effects for companies listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group over the period 2014-2023. The model specification was:

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EQTY_{it} + \beta_2 DEBT_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

The estimated coefficients and corresponding statistics are as follows:

Table 3 Random Effects Model Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C (Intercept)	0.065520	0.022448	2.918800	0.0044
EQTY	4.96x10 ⁻¹⁰	2.06 x10 ⁻¹⁰	2.414789	0.0176
DEBT	-3.79 x10 ⁻¹⁰	6.15 x10 ⁻¹¹	-6.162431	0.0000
R-squared:	0.286527			
Durbin-Watson stat:	1.241595			
Adjusted R-squared	0.271816			
Prob(F-statistic)				

Dependent Variable: ROA

Source: Researcher’s computation using E-views 8

The R-squared of 0.286527 indicates that approximately 28.65% of the variability in ROA is explained by the model after accounting for random effects. This suggests moderate fit of the model. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.241595 suggests reduced autocorrelation in the residuals. Prob(F-statistic) of 0.000000 is highly significant, indicating that the overall model is statistically significant.

The p-values of 0.0176 and 0.0000 demonstrate a significant positive relationship between equity and ROA, and a significant negative relationship between debt and ROA respectively. Based on the results, the alternative hypotheses are accepted that equity capital has positive significant impact on return on asset of firms, while debt capital has negative significant effect on ROA.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study investigates the impact of capital structure on financial performance, with focus on the impact of equity and debt capitals on return on asset (ROA) of manufacturing companies quoted on the Nigerian Exchange group. The analyses of the data obtained from the annual reports and accounts of 10 manufacturing companies from 2013 to 2023 shows that equity capital and debt capital have positive and negative significant impact on return on assets respectively.

Based on the above findings, the study concludes that capital structure significantly affects the financial performance of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Specifically, higher equity levels increase profitability and asset returns, while greater debt levels diminish them. Therefore, it is recommended that:

- ❖ Manufacturing companies should strive for a balanced capital structure that maximizes the benefits of equity while minimizing effects of excessive debt.
- ❖ Manufacturing companies should regularly monitor their debt levels not to exceed manageable thresholds.
- ❖ Managers should consider strategies to enhance equity, such as reinvesting profits or issuing new shares.
- ❖ Investors should prioritize companies that demonstrate efficient asset utilization and profitability.

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